

Designing and Calculating Multiple Digital Product Supply Chains

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While multiple industries have benefited from standardizing their production processes and conducting extensive research to optimize these supply chains in an evolving and competitive landscape (Eppen & Schrage, 1981), it is time for the digital industry to follow similar steps. The digital industry, specifically, should not be equated with traditional industries, as it faces unique challenges in developing standardized supply chains for producing digital products—whether web, mobile, software, or hybrid solutions [1]. If we take caution from history and how industries in the past faced issues when standardizing these supply chains (Lee, 1996), we should not only organize all processes but also implement a periodic review policy alongside a comprehensive backlog to further optimize the supply chain and establish the base standard that is the objective of this research: determining the multiple probabilities for a standardized supply chain for digital products [2].

The lack of literature on the specific subject of supply chain design and optimization for digital products was evident from the inception of this research. In contrast, there exists a wealth of literature addressing the reverse: the integration of software and information technology to optimize traditional supply chains, as well as advancements in logistics through machine learning and software applications.

Before commencing this research, my first task was to review all relevant literature pertaining to supply chain design and creation. This included works by David Simchi-Levi, Philip Kaminsky, and Edith Simchi-Levi, which focus on foundational supply chain principles, as well as Jeff Gothelf's insights on optimizing digital products alongside the DevOps technique by Gene Kim, Patrick Debois, John Willis, and Jez Humble. Additionally, I examined the well-known Lean and Agile movements, which emphasize efficiency and flexibility in production processes.

This extensive literature review serves as a foundational layer for my research. It is crucial to approach the design of a supply chain for digital products with caution, recognizing that the processes for industries producing physical goods differ significantly from those in sectors focused on services or digital products.

The combination of my past curriculums and professional life has always forced me to view each problem in a triple scope view: the Software Engineer view, the UI UX Designer view, and the Logistician view. In my experience with digital products, I have consistently observed that the Logistician perspective prevails in every instance. This pattern struck me as peculiar and has prompted further investigation into the reasons behind it.

[1] The video game industry should be viewed as an artistic entertainment product, similar to movies and books, which requires its own tailored supply chain and it's not the target industry for this research.

[2] The objective of this research is to determine the various probabilities involved in creating a standardized supply chain specifically for digital products.

Designing a supply chain is a substantial academic undertaking that demands extensive research and a well-established framework. In this research phase, the objective is to manually outline all possible probabilities for supply chains involved in producing a digital product. This will be achieved by establishing processes based on a decade of personal experience, as well as drawing upon public and academic knowledge, and considering possibilities that have yet to be explored in a corporate environment. Collectively, these insights will serve as samples for future testing, enabling the collection of data for comparative analysis using a quantitative approach.

Before presenting the manual variations, it's essential to distinguish between a workflow for digital products and a supply chain (or logistics) approach to producing them. While a workflow primarily maps out the internal processes required to create a product, a supply chain encompasses not only the workflow but also external factors and processes, such as procurement, outsourcing, and resource allocation—covering human, digital, and physical resources. A supply chain is a robust, standardized system designed for high-volume production across B2B and B2C contexts, handling multiple digital products or features simultaneously in a looped, efficient manner (Eppen & Schrage, 1981). Although you could consider this a workflow, it operates as a supply chain when logistics standardization is applied. In fact, we cannot achieve true standardization within digital product creation until it is framed as a supply chain.

The example supply chain presented in this research is designed, grouped, and organized to encompass the basic supply chain within a corporate environment. This includes digital agencies, collaborations between startups working on large client projects, multiple freelancers hired for the digitization of a firm, and companies developing their own digital products in the form of Software as a Service (SaaS) [3], even features can enter the loop of this supply chain.

This research presents a prototype example of a supply chain model. It is important to clarify that this is not the final or perfect design, but rather a foundational example intended for further modifications and testing regarding cost, time, and quality. The primary objective of this research is to explore all possible variations for future evaluation.

The base prototype is designed to encompass all possible options, including workflow [4], parallel ongoing flows, and external processes. This comprehensive approach facilitates the calculation of variations, allowing for the design of these variations to undergo future testing in order to identify the most optimized solution.

[3] *SaaS: Software as a Service refers to a web application provided as a subscription-based service, allowing users to pay monthly, quarterly, or annually to access these digital services.*

[4] *Workflow: Internal iterative and sequential processes within the supply chain, focusing primarily on production as its core.*

Figure 1: Prototype Supply Chain for producing digital products (Web, software, mobile)

MVP: Minimum Viable Product

The entry process: also referred to as the loop entry, serves as the critical starting point of the supply chain. This stage is where various forms of input—such as text, voice, or other relevant information—are gathered. These inputs are crucial for informing the development of digital solutions, whether they involve creating a complete digital product or adding specific features to an existing product. If the loop has already undergone its initial rotation, the entry point also facilitates iterative improvements based on stakeholder feedback, and customer support through a client's feedback and evolving requirements.

Workflow 1 - Research & Analysis: The research and analysis process is a crucial component of the internal workflow. Despite being overlooked by some producers, it remains a vital step employed by others. This process involves refining the raw data collected from the entry point and fully elaborating on it. Ultimately, this stage prepares the foundation for user experience design, ensuring that decisions are data-driven and aligned with user needs.

Workflow 2 - User Experience Design: The user experience design process centers on developing graybox wireframes and user flows based on insights from the research and analysis phase. This workflow aims to establish a clear layout and structure for the digital solution, ensuring it meets user needs effectively. Graybox wireframes provide a basic visual representation of the interface, emphasizing functionality and layout without getting into detailed design elements. User flows outline the steps users will take to navigate the product, ensuring a logical and intuitive experience. Collaboration with stakeholders during this phase is essential for gathering feedback and making iterative improvements, ultimately refining the user experience to align with project objectives.

Workflow 3 - User Interface Design & Prototyping: The user interface design and prototyping process focuses on creating high-fidelity, clickable prototypes that bring the graybox wireframes to life. This workflow aims to develop a visually appealing and interactive representation of the digital solution, allowing for realistic user interactions. The high-fidelity prototypes incorporate design elements such as colors, typography, and imagery, closely resembling the final product. Additionally, this phase emphasizes the creation of a Minimum Viable Product (MVP), which includes the core features necessary to meet user needs and validate the solution in the market. Stakeholder feedback during this stage is crucial, enabling iterative enhancements and ensuring the design aligns with user expectations and project goals.

Workflow 4 - Front End Development: The front end development process transforms high-fidelity prototypes into functional, interactive interfaces. This workflow involves translating design specifications into code using HTML and CSS, or, in a corporate environment, leveraging CSS frameworks for enhanced styling efficiency. For interactivity and functionality, JavaScript is utilized, with modular JavaScript frameworks employed in corporate settings for web, mobile, or software applications. Front end developers focus on creating responsive and accessible user interfaces that perform seamlessly across various devices and browsers. Collaboration with designers is crucial to ensure the design's integrity while implementing features. Thorough testing is conducted to identify and resolve any issues, guaranteeing that the final product delivers an optimal user experience and meets project objectives.

Workflow 5 – Back End Development: The back end development process is essential for creating the server-side logic and database interactions that power the application. This workflow involves building the application's architecture using programming languages such as Python, Ruby, Java, or PHP, along with frameworks suited for enterprise environments. Developers focus on establishing secure and efficient APIs that facilitate communication between the front end and the back end. Additionally, database management systems are implemented to store, retrieve, and manipulate data effectively. Collaboration with front end developers is crucial during this stage to ensure seamless integration and functionality. Rigorous testing and optimization are conducted to enhance performance, security, and scalability, ensuring the application meets user needs and project objectives.

Workflow 6 – Deployment and Sales: The deployment and sales process focuses on launching the application and bringing it to market. This workflow involves preparing the application for deployment, ensuring that all components are properly configured and optimized for the production environment. Key activities include setting up servers, configuring hosting services, and implementing necessary security measures. Once deployed, the sales strategy is activated to promote the application, which may involve marketing campaigns, outreach to potential clients, and leveraging sales channels. Collaboration with marketing and sales teams is essential to effectively communicate the value proposition of the product and drive user adoption. Continuous monitoring of application performance and user feedback is crucial post-launch to identify areas for improvement and inform future updates.

Output Point – Distribution Channels (Digital Stores, etc.): The distribution channels process involves identifying and establishing the pathways through which the application will reach its users. This includes various digital stores, such as app marketplaces, online platforms, and proprietary distribution channels. The focus is on optimizing the presence of the application in these channels to maximize visibility and accessibility. Strategies may include creating engaging product listings, utilizing promotional features, and managing user reviews to enhance credibility. Collaboration with marketing teams is essential to develop targeted campaigns that drive traffic and encourage downloads or purchases. Continuous analysis of distribution performance is vital to refine strategies and ensure the application effectively reaches its intended audience.

External – Customer Support: This process is essential for maintaining user satisfaction and fostering long-term client relationships. It establishes various support channels, such as help desks and chat support, to provide timely solutions to user inquiries. Integrating reverse logistics, the process efficiently manages product returns, exchanges, and refunds, ensuring a seamless experience for customers. A well-trained support team addresses diverse concerns and gathers feedback to identify areas for improvement. Continuous enhancement of support processes contributes to overall user experience and loyalty, while effective reverse logistics maintains positive relationships even after the sale.

External – Vendor and Provisions: This process focuses on establishing and managing relationships with external vendors and suppliers to ensure a steady flow of necessary resources and services. Effective vendor management involves evaluating and selecting vendors based on criteria such as reliability, quality, and cost. Collaboration with these partners is crucial for maintaining timely delivery of materials and services that support the overall supply chain. Additionally, this phase includes negotiating contracts, monitoring vendor performance, and ensuring compliance with agreements. By optimizing vendor relationships and provisions, organizations can enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and improve the quality of their offerings.

Parallel – Marketing & Promotion: This process runs concurrently with other workflows, focusing on creating awareness and driving engagement for the product. Effective marketing strategies involve identifying target audiences, developing compelling messaging, and utilizing various channels such as social media, email campaigns, and online advertising. Promotion efforts may include special offers, partnerships, and influencer collaborations to boost visibility and attract users. Continuous analysis of marketing performance is essential for refining strategies and optimizing outreach efforts. By aligning marketing and promotion activities with product development, organizations can enhance brand presence and accelerate user acquisition.

Parallel – R&D and Improvement [5]: This process focuses on ongoing research and development to enhance the product and adapt to changing market demands. Operating independently, it can also be informed by insights gathered from customer support and maintenance activities. The R&D process involves analyzing user feedback, identifying areas for innovation, and testing new features or enhancements. By fostering a culture of continuous improvement, organizations can ensure that their offerings remain competitive and relevant. This iterative approach not only improves the user experience but also drives long-term growth and adaptability in the marketplace.

Parallel – Human Resources Management & Training: This process focuses on managing personnel and fostering a culture of continuous learning within the organization. Human resources (HR) teams are responsible for recruiting, onboarding, and retaining talent while ensuring compliance with labor laws and company policies. Parallel to these activities, training programs are developed to enhance employee skills and knowledge, promoting professional growth and improving overall performance. Regular assessments of training effectiveness inform updates and adjustments to programs, ensuring alignment with organizational goals. By prioritizing HR management and training, organizations can build a motivated workforce capable of driving innovation and achieving business objectives.

[5] In large digital corporations, this process has its own dedicated teams, but in mid-sized to small companies, it involves the leads of each internal workflow who conduct weekly or monthly meetings to brainstorm and discuss improvements while conducting their research.

Differentiation Point [6] – Quality Assurance & Audit: This phase emphasizes the importance of maintaining high standards throughout the product development lifecycle. Quality assurance (QA) involves systematic processes to ensure that products meet specified requirements and function as intended. Regular audits are conducted to assess compliance with industry standards and internal guidelines, identifying areas for improvement. This proactive approach not only helps to prevent defects and enhance product reliability but also builds trust with customers by delivering consistent quality. By integrating quality assurance and auditing into the workflow, organizations can differentiate themselves in the market, ensuring that their offerings stand out for their reliability and excellence.

Link Process [7] – Maintenance: This process focuses on ensuring the ongoing functionality and reliability of products post-deployment. It involves regular updates, bug fixes, and performance enhancements to address user feedback and evolving needs. Maintenance activities may also include monitoring system health, conducting routine checks, and implementing necessary changes to prevent downtime. By maintaining a proactive approach to maintenance, organizations can enhance user satisfaction, extend product lifespan, and minimize disruptions in service. This continuous improvement cycle not only safeguards the quality of the product but also reinforces customer trust and loyalty.

[6] It highlights the role of logistics in service operations and discusses differentiation through quality assurance and customer service in logistics processes (Johnston, R., & Clark, G, 2005 et al).

[7] The Maintenance process acts as a link that bootstraps the supply chain as a whole by sending data independently or by customer supports to R&D, the latter restarts the input of the loop.

With the base prototype established, the next objective is to generate all possible variations. This research aims to present multiple scenarios for an optimized supply chain, each of which will undergo future testing to identify the most effective configuration.

Knowing that the workflow should remain static, except for the research process, which can be integrated into the UX process, the parallel processes and vendors & provisions can be simulated or interchanged, while the input and output processes will also remain fixed. What is the total number of possible variations from the base prototype?

Let's define the following variables:

Workflow static variable: **W** (Fixed)

Research process within the workflow: **Rw** (Can be removed from equation, which in reality fused into UX)

R&D : **D**

Marketing: **M**

Maintenance: **Mt** (Can be removed from equation, which in reality fused into R&D)

Customer Support: **Cs**

Deployment & Sales: **Ds**

HR & Training: **H**

Vendor 1: **V1** (Can be fused with V2, V3, V4)

Vendor 2: **V2** (Can be fused with V1, V3, V4)

Vendor 3: **V3** (Can be fused with V1, V2, V4)

Vendor 4: **V4** (Can be fused with V1, V2, V3)

Q/A 1 (UI to Front): **Q1**

Q/A 2 (Front to Back): **Q2**

Q/A 3 (Back to Deploy): **Q3**

Distribution: **Dt**

Vendor 1: **V1** (Can be fused with V2, V3, V4)

Vendor 2: **V2** (Can be fused with V1, V3, V4)

Vendor 3: **V3** (Can be fused with V1, V2, V4)

Vendor 4: **V4** (Can be fused with V1, V2, V3)

Q/A 1 (UI to Front): **Q1**

Q/A 2 (Front to Back): **Q2**

Q/A 3 (Back to Deploy): **Q3**

Distribution: **Dt**

Logic:

W: 1 Option => W=1

Rw: 2 Options (Fused into UX) or remains independent => Rw=2

D: Can start only after front end, from the start of the supply chain, or only post deployment
=> D=3

M: Can start mid backend, from the start of the supply chain, or when the MVP is available
after UI process => M=3

Mt: Can be fused into R&D or remain independent => Mt=2

Cs: Fixed, only 1 option => Cs=1

Ds: Fixed, only 1 option => Ds=1

H: Option with the training alone, or HR plus training => H=2

V1 to V4: (2^4) => $V(n) = 16$ ($n < 5$ AND $n > 0$)

Q1 to Q3= (2^3) => $Q(n) = 8$ ($n < 4$ AND $n > 0$)

Dt: Fixed, only 1 option => Dt=1

Function:

Defining T as the total probabilities:

$$T = W \times R_w \times D \times M \times M_t \times C_s \times D_s \times H \times V(n) \times Q(n) \times D_t$$

$$T = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \times 1 \times 2 \times 16 \times 8 \times 1$$

$$T = 9216$$

Conclusion:

The analysis of the total probability of variations within the supply chain design yielded an overwhelming figure of 9216 possible configurations. This vast number of variations presents a significant challenge, making it impractical to test each one thoroughly. Given the complexity and resource constraints of conducting extensive tests [8] on all potential supply chain variations, a more efficient approach is necessary.

To streamline the evaluation process, it is essential to leverage machine learning techniques that can intelligently sift through the data. By training algorithms to identify patterns and predict outcomes, we can effectively root out the less viable variations, focusing our efforts on those configurations that demonstrate the greatest potential for success. This first-round filtration will not only reduce the number of variations to a manageable size but also enhance the likelihood of discovering optimized solutions. In doing so, we can ensure that subsequent testing is both efficient and targeted, ultimately leading to a more effective supply chain design.

[8] A single test of a supply chain can take between 2 to 3 months in simulation.

Using machine learning, we can develop an algorithm capable of optimizing the variations and eliminating unsuccessful configurations through the use of knowledge bases, data sheets, and neural network navigation. Our objective is for the AI interface resulting from this algorithm to present detailed insights into the best possible variations, including the original prototype. This approach will enable us to harness the power of AI to streamline decision-making and enhance the effectiveness of our supply chain design.

First, I have to create a knowledge base for the machine to use and simulate the variations. The CSV file will include the following, based on the calculations we've done previously concerning the prototype:

Process	Variations	Importance
Workflow (W)	1	3
Research & Analysis (Rw)	2	2
Development (D)	3	3
Marketing (M)	3	3
Maintenance (M)	2	2
Customer Support (Cs)	1	1
Deployment & Sales (Ds)	1	3
HR & Training (H)	2	1
Vendor Options (V1 to V4)	16	3
Quality Assurance (Q1 to Q3)	8	3
Distribution (Dt)	1	3

Table 1: Structure of the CSV knowledge base as preparation for the machine.

```
import pandas as pd
import sys
from collections import deque

def main():
    # Ensure a CSV file is provided
    if len(sys.argv) != 2:
        print("Usage: python supplychains.py <csv_file>")
        return

    csv_file = sys.argv[1]

    try:
        # Read the CSV file
        data = pd.read_csv(csv_file, sep=';')

        # Ensure the correct number of columns
        if data.shape[1] < 3:
            print("CSV file must have at least three columns: Process, Variations, Importance.")
            return

        # Convert the 'Variations' column to numeric
        data['Variations'] = pd.to_numeric(data['Variations'], errors='coerce')

        # Check for NaN values after conversion
        if data['Variations'].isnull().any():
            print("Warning: Some variations could not be converted to numbers and will be ignored.")

        # Queue for storing important variations
        queue = deque()
```

Figure 2: Part 1 of the Python code for the basic data processing algorithm to optimize the supply chains variations as a base for the machine learning model.

```
# Enqueue important variations based on their importance
for index, row in data.iterrows():
    if row.iloc[2] in [2, 3]: # Check Importance
        queue.append(row)

# Optimize: reduce the number of variations to those with importance
optimized_variations = []
total_probabilities = 1 # Start with 1 for multiplication

while queue:
    item = queue.popleft()
    variation_value = item['Variations']

    # Only include valid variation values (non-NaN) in the product
    if not pd.isnull(variation_value):
        optimized_variations.append(item)
        total_probabilities *= variation_value # Use multiplication
        print(f"Processing item: {item}, current total: {total_probabilities}")

# Print the important variations and total probabilities
print("\nImportant Variations (Optimized):")
for variation in optimized_variations:
    print(variation)

print(f"\nTotal Probabilities of Important Variations (Product): {total_probabilities}")

# Check the number of optimized variations
print(f"\nTotal Optimized Variations Count: {len(optimized_variations)}")

except Exception as e:
    print(f"An error occurred: {e}")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

Figure 3: Part 2 of the Python code for the basic data processing algorithm to optimize the supply chains variations as a base for the machine learning model.

```

PROBLEMS  OUTPUT  DEBUG CONSOLE  TERMINAL  PORTS
Importance 3
Description Phases from start to post-deployment.
Name: 2, dtype: object
Process Marketing (M)
Variations 3
Importance 3
Description Can start mid-backend or with MVP.
Name: 3, dtype: object
Process Maintenance (Mt)
Variations 2
Importance 2
Description Can be fused into R&D or remain independent.
Name: 4, dtype: object
Process Human Resources & Training (H)
Variations 2
Importance 2
Description Training alone or HR plus training.
Name: 7, dtype: object
Process Vendor Options (V1 to V4)
Variations 16
Importance 3
Description Options to combine vendors.
Name: 8, dtype: object
Process Quality Assurance (Q1 to Q3)
Variations 8
Importance 3
Description QA phases across the development cycle.
Name: 9, dtype: object

Total Probabilities of Important Variations: 37

```

Figure 4: Console results of the optimization code.

The optimization algorithm in its first phase has proven useful, producing a result of 37 probabilities, which represents a reduction of 99.6% from the original 4608 variations. While this is a significant achievement, conducting 37 successive tests, each taking between 2 to 3 months, is still not optimal. Therefore, our objective now is to refine the data for the machine learning algorithm further.

The first refinement will focus on the vendor variations (V(n)). From the original 16 options, we will retain only 2: one where all four vendors remain as separate processes within the supply chain, and another where we fuse the Research, UX, and UI vendors together, along with the two vendors related to the front and back end.

The second refinement will address quality assurance, consolidating it into a single variation due to its critical importance. Each process will remain the same as outlined in the prototype supply chain.

Process	Variations	Importance
Workflow (W)	1	3
Research & Analysis (Rw)	2	2
Development (D)	3	3
Marketing (M)	3	3
Maintenance (M)	2	2
Customer Support (Cs)	1	1
Deployment & Sales (Ds)	1	3
HR & Training (H)	2	1
Vendor Options (V1 to V4)	2	3
Quality Assurance (Q1 to Q3)	1	3
Distribution (Dt)	1	3

Table 2: Refinement 1 of the supply chain variation data

```

Process                Development (D)
Variations              3
Importance              3
Description             Phases from start to post-deployment.
Name: 2, dtype: object
Process                Marketing (M)
Variations              3
Importance              3
Description             Can start mid-backend on with MVP.
Name: 3, dtype: object
Process                Maintenance (Mt)
Variations              2
Importance              2
Description             Can be fused into R&D or remain independent.
Name: 4, dtype: object
Process                Human Resources & Training (H)
Variations              2
Importance              2
Description             Training alone or HR plus training.
Name: 7, dtype: object
Process                Vendor Options (V1 to V4)
Variations              2
Importance              3
Description             Options to combine vendors.
Name: 8, dtype: object
Process                Quality Assurance (Q1 to Q3)
Variations              1
Importance              3
Description             QA phases across the development cycle.
Name: 9, dtype: object

Total Probabilities of Important Variations: 16
PS C:\Users\zinef\Desktop\Research1\AI-Variations>

```

Figure 5: Console results for the first refinement

The result post-refinement is 16 variations of the prototype supply chain, representing a percentage cut of approximately 56.8% from the initial 37 variations. If I had the resources to conduct all 16 variations through parallel simulation, I would have considered halting the refinement rounds at this point. However, 16 variations remain a high number and an impractical task for independent research. Therefore, I had to introduce an additional refinement layer to further reduce the total number of variations, implementing the following adjustments:

1- Marketing (M): Reduced to 2 options only: starting from the beginning of the supply chain continuously in parallel, or initiating during the backend phase. This adjustment consolidates the previous mid-way options into one streamlined choice.

2- Research & Development (D): Reduced to only 1 option, as this represents the most optimized path and serves as a quality booster. The samples we need must meet the trio of criteria: Quality, Time, and Cost.

3- Human Resources & Training (H): Also reduced to just 1 option to streamline processes and enhance efficiency.

4- Maintenance (Mt): Reduced to only 1 option to simplify the workflow and ensure consistency.

5- Research Process & Analysis (Rw): Keeping it separate from the UX research and Design. 1 Option only.

Process	Variations	Importance
Workflow (W)	1	3
Research & Analysis (Rw)	1	2
Development (D)	1	3
Marketing (M)	2	3
Maintenance (M)	2	2
Customer Support (Cs)	2	1
Deployment & Sales (Ds)	1	3
HR & Training (H)	1	1
Vendor Options (V1 to V4)	4	3
Quality Assurance (Q1 to Q3)	1	3
Distribution (Dt)	1	3

Table 3: Refinement 2 of the supply chain variation data.

```

PROBLEMS  OUTPUT  DEBUG CONSOLE  TERMINAL  PORTS

Name: 1, dtype: object
Process           Development (D)
Variations                1
Importance                3
Description        Phases from start to post-deployment.
Name: 2, dtype: object
Process           Marketing (M)
Variations                2
Importance                3
Description        Can start mid-backend or with MVP.
Name: 3, dtype: object
Process           Maintenance (ME)
Variations                1
Importance                2
Description        Can be fused into R&D or remain independent.
Name: 4, dtype: object
Process           Human Resources & Training (H)
Variations                1
Importance                2
Description        Training alone or HR plus training.
Name: 7, dtype: object
Process           Vendor Options (V1 to V4)
Variations                2
Importance                3
Description        Options to combine vendors.
Name: 8, dtype: object
Process           Quality Assurance (Q1 to Q3)
Variations                1
Importance                3
Description        QA phases across the development cycle.
Name: 9, dtype: object

Total Probabilities of Important Variations (Product): 4
PS C:\Users\zinef\Desktop\Research\AI-Variations> ]

```

Figure 6: Console results post the second refinement.

The result of having only 4 variations is far better than I anticipated. Thanks to the algorithm's simulation and the subsequent refinements, we achieved an impressive 99.96% optimization from an initial 9216 variations. This reduction allows us to design a manageable set of variations for the prototype supply chain, which will undergo proper testing in a corporate environment. This approach will ensure accurate measurements regarding its feasibility and provide a realistic perspective on its potential for future success.

This research represents the initial step toward designing the most optimized supply chain for digital products. It encompasses the processes of prototyping, calculating probabilities, and refining variations through the algorithm developed specifically for this study. The end result is a set of variations that will undergo rigorous testing and full production in a corporate environment. Over the course of several months, we will measure each process to gather essential data, which will be subject to observation and analysis for further optimization. This ongoing effort aims to establish a standardized supply chain tailored for software, web, and mobile application production.

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